

INFORMATION SOURCES AND PREMARITAL SEX AMONG TEENAGERS IN UYO URBAN COMMUNITIES OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

Joyce Eminue Ibia

Public Order and Information Management
University of Uyo, Uyo
Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to investigate the influence of information sources on premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The impact of older siblings' sexual conversations, peer group pressure and social media images of premarital sex were investigated. Three objectives, research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Expost facto research design was used from a population of 4791 Senior Secondary two (SS2) students, a sample size of 364 (52 samples in each of the seven out of 14 public secondary schools in Uyo) was drawn through the stratified random sampling technique using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. A validated instrument, Information Sources and Premarital Sex Questionnaire (LSPSQ) with a reliability index of .84 was used to gather data for the study. Simple Linear Regression was used to analyze data collected at .05 alpha level, Results revealed a significant influence of older siblings' sexual conversations, peer group pressure and social media images as information sources predisposing teenagers to premarital sex in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It was recommended among other things that older siblings should be discouraged by parents, health educators and religious leaders not to generate sexual conversations that could mislead their younger ones into engaging in premarital sex. Teenagers should restrict themselves from promiscuous friends; and parents, teachers and religious leaders should educate teenagers on the dangers of using social media to download pornographic materials which could make them copy the sexual behaviour of characters they see on the internet.

KEYWORDS: Information sources, teenagers, older siblings, Peer group, Premarital Sex

INTRODUCTION

Information sources are generally believed to exert tremendous influence on the decision-making process of people either positively or negatively; especially teenagers. Information brings about knowledge. Knowledge itself is power; lack of it is depilating. As aptly noted by Hills and Argyle (2013), knowledge empowers people, especially teenagers to form their own opinions, to act and transform conditions leading perhaps to a better quality of life. Access to the right information at the right time gives teenagers greater control over their

destinies.

According to Adomi (2012), information sources are those sources of information which individuals gain knowledge from to build a life that can affect oneself in any social setting. The author noted further that information sources enable especially teenagers to become more informed, empowered and actively participate in the decision-making process about their life endeavours. Information sources also provide teenagers with information about their sexuality and sexual behaviours. Information sources are conceptualized in this study as sources of information that tend to influence the socio-emotional attitude of teenagers toward premarital sexual activities. Teenagers as used in this study also refer to the period of adolescence defined by World Health Organization (WHO) (2011) as a period covering the age range of 10 -19 years. Like any other stage of human development, the teenage period is an important stage of physical and psychological human development which generally occurs from puberty to adulthood and is characterized by sexual maturity and the ability to reproduce (Armett, 2011).

An important aspect of the biological changes during puberty is that they brings about the release of sexual hormones that affect emotions (Anwana, 2012). The mood changes in teenagers may increase which could positively or negatively influence their relationships at home with parents, and siblings and at school with peers and significant others. As aptly noted by Kalgo, (2012), this is because teenagers often acquire information from diverse sources at an early stage, especially in this era of E – Information Communication Technology (ICT) which could influence their disposition to premarital sexual activities.

Based perhaps on the above, Bankole, Biddlecom, Gulella, Singh and Zulu (2017) cautioned that information concerning teenagers' sexual orientation should be unique and quantitative to be beneficial to them and improve their sexual behaviours. Thus, teenagers whose information regarding premarital sexual activities is from secure sources tend to utilize it with a positive attitude, while those who receive information from unsecured sources may likely exhibit it negatively.

Teenagers' attitude to premarital sexual activities in this study refers to their mindset, predisposition or relative attraction towards sexual activities. Attitude can be viewed as the degree of attractiveness an individual teenager possesses as a behavioural goal. Akinade (2014) observed that sexual attraction is an important aspect of the sexuality of persons being observed as well as the person observing. Individual teenager determines the information source and qualities he/she finds sexually attractive. Breuner and Mattson (2018) also noted correctly that all teenager needs is to receive accurate and educative information about sexuality and to understand ultimately how to practice healthy sexual behaviour. Jackson, Henderson, Frank and Haw (2012) opined that the type of information a teenager receives may lead to health and social problems such as unintended parenthood and or Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIS).

Premarital sex is conceptualized in this study as sexual activities practised by people before marriage. Such sexual practice according to Akinade (2014) includes conduct and activities intended to arouse the sexual interests of others. The authors opined further that it includes the degree of enduring romantic, sexual, affection, emotional and physical attraction to other members of the opposite sex, same-sex or both.

Historically, premarital sex was considered taboo and was seriously frowned upon in many cultures in the world. Religiously, it was considered a sin by members of religious

groups. Currently, we are experiencing a shift from premarital abstinence to liberal sexual activities contrary to the demand of most African cultures whereby getting married as a virgin was held in a very high esteem. Teenagers are currently more sexually active than before probably because they mature early, are exposed to urban influences, the internet, and changing traditional values and norms (Folayan, Adebajo, Adeyemi and Ogunbami, 2015). Teenagers in recent times are in the age of E-Information Communication Technology (ICT) and also acquire information from various sources at a very early age that influences their attitude toward premarital sex.

The premarital pervasiveness of teenagers has been of serious concerns to parents, guardians, and educational stakeholders and religious leaders. It appears there has not been a comprehensive sexuality education early in life for teenagers that could prepare their minds against sexual promiscuity of the twenty-first century aimed at life-long adjustment against sexual pressure in the world presently which differ significantly from the pressure of the passed centuries.

Teenager or adolescence is a period that ushers individuals into the world of pleasurable experience filled with excitement and desire for sexual adventures. According to the United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) (2011), teenager or adolescent is a period filled with curiosity and exploration about the world as well as their bodies. However, and as aptly noted by Isangedighi (2002), in Nigeria, cultural and religious beliefs have denied teenagers the opportunity of receiving enough information about human sexuality. Thus, when accurate information is not available, teenagers will ignorantly accept miss information for Truth, and this is particularly noticeable among teenagers concerning premarital sex (CorderBolz, 2012).

Older siblings' sex conversations in the family could influence teenagers decision making process positively or negative with regards to premarital sex. Sexual conversions in this paper is defined as an information source that could influence the socio-emotional attitude of teenagers toward engaging in premarital sexual activities According to Gershoff and Grogan-Kaylor (2016), teenagers learn by examples, the most influential role models in teenagers' lives are their older siblings. Older siblings must act as models at home on how they want their younger siblings to behave. Unfortunately, as correctly noted by Effiong (2012), some older siblings in the home environments sometimes generate conversations about sex that often mislead the younger ones into trying sexual intercourse. In the opinion of Harris (2014), this they do despite the conservative environments of the home that disapprove of sexual discussions among teenagers. The author stated further that irrespective of parental restrictions, teenagers always create opportunities for sibling sexual interactions. The truth is that the positive and negative information from older siblings during interactions regarding their sexual relationship experiences may likely lure the younger ones into premarital sexual activities.

Much of the information about sex that teenagers come in contact with may be through direct experience with peer groups. According to Ibia (2010), the peer group is an association of people within the same age group to which an individual within the community belongs and has equal status with other members. The author noted further that peer group is one major factor motivating teenagers' attitudes and behaviour so that they become more similar and more acceptable to other group members because they have their own rules, code of conduct, membership norms and traditions. Consequently, they exert a powerful influence

on the teenager as the rules of the peer group become the commandment of the teenager and his/her personality is greatly influenced by the group.

For most teenagers, their peer group may be a principal source of information about sex. The premarital sexual behaviour of teenagers will more likely be influenced by what they believe their peers are doing to have a sense of belonging (Markson and Kings, 2016). According to Cordex-Bolz (2011), most teenagers are lured into premarital sex relationships by their peers who may have experienced sex in one way or the other. Cavanah (2014) also noted that having a large network of friends that includes a higher proportion of older or opposite sex may be associated with premarital sex among teenagers.

According to Ubom (2013), incidence of drug use and premarital sex are related and are always transmitted by veteran members of the peer group. The author stated further that refusal by the naïve or neophyte members to engage in the culture often earn such a member excommunication from the group. Since many teenagers want to retain their membership, they have to comply. Thus, precocious sexual activities among teenagers maybe due to social contacts with veteran members of their group.

Teenagers in recent times are in the era of e-information communication technology (ICT) and probably be privy' to information in social media. Wikipedia, the Free Press Encyclopedia (2012) defines social media as a web and mobile-based technology that supports interactive dialogue and introduces substantial and pervasive changes in communications between organizations, communities and individuals. In essence, social media which is a powerful tool for conducting education, research, business and governmental affairs is often time misused by teenagers who now use mobile and web-based technologies to create interactive platforms where they share, co-create and modify content from which they benefit. Based on the above, Ibia (2016) stated that for teenagers in Nigeria, social media represents an experiment to do what they feel is good or exciting and at the same time avoid adult supervision.

Social media commonly used by teenagers include Facebook, Twitter, Blackberry Messenger, WhatsApp, Skype, 2go Badoo, LinkedIn, YouTube, Hicker and Timber. Of these, Facebook, Twitter and YouTube are the most popular, Livingstone (2008), Beech, Elliot, Briden and Finder (2008) have correctly noted that teenagers exposed to social media through cell phones via the internet use unconventional or undesirable speech at its peak, seek negative attention, rebel against authority figures and questions rules, boundaries and societal norms. These scholars noted further that they also engage in premarital sex against cultural norms and values. The scenario according to Ibia (2016) is ominous for both the teenagers involved and the society at large.

Biswajit and lyoti (2011) have stated correctly that one of the purposes of social media is to make contact with people and build a network of healthy relationships in society. Therefore, accessibility to information through social media has made it possible for teenagers with common beliefs to find each other and reinforce premarital sexual behaviours considered by most members of society as unacceptable. Indeed, Rogers, Smoke and Liu (2006) have observed that social media usage presents some teenagers with unique opportunities to be initiated into premarital sex. Similarly, Dohring (2009) observes that sexually related online activities have become routine in recent years for a large population of teenagers and that exposure to sexual images in social media has consistently been associated with increased initiation into premarital sex, more sexual partners and higher risk of

unplanned pregnancies.

Theoretically, this study is based on the foundation of Bandura's (1996) Sexual Cognitive Theory of Mass Communication. Given the prevalence of sexual content in popular social media available to teenagers, it is safe to assume that media portrayal of sex as fun, careless and common activity that does not warrant concerns, cautions, contraception or consequences may have made teenagers cultivate similar beliefs and have consequently influenced their attitude toward premarital sex. Exposure to sexual content in the media may have also primed teenagers, sensitizing them to sexualized attitudes and behaviors. A good example is the Cultivation Theory by Goerner, Cross, Morgan and Signorelli (1994) which proposes that media portrayal of sexual behaviour is more extensive and powerful than the limited life experiences of teenagers and is more consistent with virtual reality than reality itself.

Since teenagers use the media more often, the media overwhelms the information they receive from real-world peers and significant others. The result is that the media personalities become super peers", engaging teenagers" appreciation, and demonstrating how fictional teens think, act, and function as virtual role models for those who are figuring out how they are and how they should behave as sexual beings (Straburger and Wilson 2008). It can be said that teenagers exposed to sexual content in social media are disinherited by such exposures to media betrayal of premarital casual sex, allowing them to vicariously explore experiences that have been frowned upon by parents, guardians, authority figures and by 'real life' rules and norms of the society.

Globally, the early onset of sexual activities among teenagers is on the increase. Teenagers are currently more sexually active than before probably because they mature early and are exposed to urban influences and changing traditional values and norms. In Uyo, the capital city of Akwa Ibom State as well as other urban centers in Nigeria, people are experiencing a shift from sexual abstinence before marriage to liberal premarital sex contrary to hitherto values and norms of most Nigerian culture. Socialization through sexual talks, sexual behaviour from older siblings, peer group pressure sexual images in social media and other diverse information sources tend to compel and attract teenagers to explore and experience premarital sex without conscious decisions and considerations of the outcomes.

Sexuality information sources are identifiable and real; yet, there has not been a corresponding comprehensive sexuality education early enough in the lives of teenagers to equip them with skills for life-long self-adjustment, informed decision making and choices concerning premarital sexual activities. Teenagers' beliefs, expectations and attraction to sex and sexual behaviour are influenced by information sources on sexuality. Against this background, this study sought to determine the influence of older siblings" sexual conversations, peer group pressure influence and social media image as information sources on premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of the study was to investigate influence of information sources on premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed at:

1. Determining the influence of older siblings" sexual conversations on premarital sex amongst teenagers.

2. Ascertaining the influence of peer group on premarital sex of teenagers.
3. Assessing the influence of social media images on premarital sex of teenagers.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. Older siblings' sexual conversations do not significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State Nigeria.
2. Peer group pressure does not significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
3. Social media images do not significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the ex-post-facto research design. because the researcher had no direct control of the independent variables since their manifestation had already occurred or because they are inherently manipulable. Borg and Gall (2004), Kerlinger (2000) and Udo and Joseph (2005) have correctly noted that the ex-post facto research design method is often used instead of experimental design to test hypotheses about cause and effect relationships among variables that cannot be manipulated experimentally. This design therefore enabled the researcher to test hypotheses about the cause-and-effect relationship among variables for premarital sexual activities of teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Denga and Ali (2000) have commended this design for effective generalization across the parent population with some high degree of precision.

The target population for the study consisted of all the 4791 Senior Secondary Two (SS2) students in all the fourteenth (14) public secondary schools in Uyo (State Secondary Education Board, Statistics Division (2024)). The choice of this level of students was considered appropriate because they fall between the age range of 10-19 years classified by the World Health Organization (WHO) (2011) as adolescents or teenagers. This group of students were considered mature, exposed enough and may have exhibited sexual behaviour tendencies and would be in a better position to respond to items of the questionnaire instrument.

A sample size of 364 respondents (52 in each of the seven secondary schools selected for the study) was drawn through the stratified random sampling technique using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size determination table. These scholars observed that as the population increases, the sample size increases at diminishing rate. Hence, for a population of about 100-110, a sample size of between 80-86 suffices and for a population size of between 1000 - 1,00000 a sample size of 278-384 suffices.

The researcher-developed instrument, Information Sources and Premarital Sex Questionnaire (ISPSQ) was used for data collection for the study. The face and content validity of the ISPSQ instrument was provided by three experts, two in Measurement and evaluation and one from the Department of Public Order and Information Management all in the University of Uyo. These experts dropped unsuitable, ambiguous and wrongly worded items before the instrument was administered. Cronbach's alpha was used to calculate the reliability of the instrument and the obtained reliability coefficient of .84 was considered by

Measurement and Evaluation experts as high reliability index for the instrument to be used for data collection for the study. Data collection was done by the researcher. This took seven days, one day in each of the seven schools selected for the study using a systematic random sampling technique. This ensures a 100 per cent return rate of the instrument. However, only 300 out of 364 questionnaires administered were correctly completed and used for data analysis for the study. The questionnaires were scored and analyzed at a .05 level of significance using Simple Linear Regression analyses.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: Older siblings' sexual conversations do not significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers.

Table 1: Simple Linear Regression of the Influence of Older Siblings' Sexual Conversations on Teenagers Premarital Sex in Uyo Urban Communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
n=300

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	Sig.	Decision
Regression	864.11	1	864.11	80.76*	.00	Reject
Residual	3189.07	298	10.28			
Total	4053.18	299				

*significant $p < .05$; $df=1,298$, $F\text{-critical}=3.87$

The result of the data analysis in Table 1 reveals a significant influence of older siblings' sexual conversations on premarital sex among teenagers. The calculated F-value of 80.76 at 1,298 degrees of freedom was found to be significantly higher than the F-critical value of 3.87. The result equally reveal that the p-value of .00 is less than .05 level of significant. Hence, the null hypothesis that predicted no significant influence of older siblings' sexual conversations on teenagers' premarital sex was rejected; meaning that older siblings' sexual conversations significantly influences premarital sex of teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Peer group pressure does significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Simple Linear Regression Analyses of the Influence of Peer Group on Premarital Sex amongst Teenagers in Uyo Urban Communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
n=300

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	Sig.	Decision
Regression	989.29	1	989.29	96.23	.00	Reject
Residual	3063.89	298	10.28			
Total	4053.18	299				

*Significant $p < .05$; $df=1,298$, $F\text{-critical}=3.87$

The result of the data analysis in Table 2 reveals a significant influence of peer group pressure on the premarital sex of teenagers. The calculated F-value of 96.23 at 1,298 degrees

of freedom was found to be significantly higher than the F-critical value of 3.87. The result in Table 2 equally reveals that the p-value of .00 was less than the .05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis that had predicted no significant influence of peer group pressure on premarital sex amongst teenagers was rejected; meaning that a significant influence exists between peer group pressure and premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: Social Media Images do not significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Images on Premarital Sex of Teenagers in Uyo Urban Communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.
n=300

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F-cal	Sig.	Decision
Regression	943.51	1	943.51	90.38*	.00	Reject
Residual	3109.67	298	10.44			
Total	4053.18	299				

*significant $p < .05$; $df = 1, 298$, $F\text{-critical} = 3.87$

The data analysis in Table 3 reveals a significant influence of social media images on premarital sex amongst teenagers. The calculated F-value of 90.38 at 1,298 degrees of freedom was found to be significantly higher than the F-critical value of 3.87. The result in Table 3 also reveals that the p-value of .00 was less than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis that had predicted no significant influence of social media images on premarital sex of teenagers was rejected; meaning that social media images significantly influence premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of data analysis on hypothesis one revealed a significant influence of older siblings' sexual conversations on teenagers' premarital sex. This finding is in agreement with earlier study findings by Akinade (2014), Effiong (2012) Gershoff and Gregan- Kaylor(2016) who in their separate study findings correctly noted that older siblings' at home environment sometimes generate sexual conversations that oftentimes mislead their younger ones to experiment sexual intercourse. Truth as stated by Akinade(2014) and Effiong (2012) is that secure attachment in sibling-sibling relationships and effective communication patterns at home despite parental restrictions often have a tremendous influence on the sexual orientation of teenagers resulting to premarital sex against societal norms. Children learn by example. Therefore, the most influential role model in the life of teenagers is their older siblings. The positive and the negative information from older siblings during some

interactions at home concerning their sexual relationship experiences often lure teenagers into premarital sexual activities.

The result of data analysis on hypothesis two revealed a significant influence of peer group pressure on premarital sex amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State. This finding corroborates earlier research findings by Cavanah (2014); Cordox-Bol (2011); Effiong (2017); Martson and King (2016) and Ubom (2012). These scholars noted in their separate study findings that most teenagers are lured into premarital sexual relationships by their peers who may have experienced sex in one way or the other. Effiong's (2017) study finding averred further that peer group members with flirting sexual tendencies often lure others into premarital sexual activities. Ubom's (2013) study finding stated further that the incidence of drug abuse and premarital sex are related and are always transmitted by veteran members of peer groups to which an individual teenager belongs. Implied from the above is the fact that for most teenagers, their peer group is the principal source of information about premarital sexual activities since most teenagers would want to do what their peers are doing to feel a sense of belonging.

The result of data analysis on hypothesis three revealed a significant influence of social media images on the premarital sex of teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. This finding supports earlier study findings by Dehring (2009), Ibia (2016), Ringrose, et.al (2012) and Gerbner et.al (1994) that teenagers exposed to sexual images in social media are associated with an increased risk of sexual behaviour, initiation into premarital sex with more sexual partners.

Indeed, Biswaji *et.al* (2011) and Ibia's (2016) study findings went further by stating that accessibility to sexual information through social media has made it possible for teenagers with common beliefs to find each other and reinforce premarital sexual activities. Judging from the above, it can be said that teenagers exposed to sexual images on social media are disinherited by such exposure to social media betrayal of premarital casual sex as fun and have allowed themselves to vicariously explore the experience that has been frowned upon by parents, guardians, authority figures and by "real life" rules and norms of the larger society (Straburger *et.al.*, 2008).

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that information sources viz older siblings, peer group pressure and social media images have communicated to teenagers, messages that have created meaning to attract them into premarital sexual activities. Generally, children learn by example. Secure attachment in sibling-sibling relationships and effective communication by older siblings at home of their sexual experiences have tremendously influenced the sexual orientation of teenagers towards premarital sexual activities in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

The peer group is a principal source of information to their members concerning sex. Most teenagers are lured into premarital sexual relationships by their veteran members. Since most teenagers want to retain membership in their group, they engage in premarital sex in order to avoid excommunication from their groups.

Although social media certainly has potential for educational uses and day-to-day communications, teenagers now use it for destructive purposes of creating interactive platforms whereby they share, co-create and modify especially pornographic materials which

they benefit. The material they create or modify is enormous and is morally corrupt and spiritually destructive. It makes teenagers lose track of discipline. As such, long exposure to morally corrupt and sexually explicit content in social media has resulted in increased premarital sexual activities amongst teenagers in Uyo urban communities of Akwa Ibom State Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made based on the findings and conclusion of the study.

1. Older siblings should be persuaded by parents, health educators and religious leaders not to generate sexual conversations that could mislead the younger ones into premarital sex in the home environment. Both older and younger siblings should be reminded that in most African societies, getting married as a virgin is still held in very high esteem.
2. Teenagers should take responsibility of restricting themselves from promiscuous sexual friends. Parents and guardians should also monitor the type of friends their children and wards keep because peer group tends to influence members into engaging in premarital sexual relationships.
3. Parents, guardians and school counsellors should educate teenagers on the danger of using social media to connect each other and establish virtual friendship that often times end up in premarital sexual relationships.

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